

SIGNIFICANCE OF NATIONAL VALUES IN FAMILY EDUCATION IN PUBLIC PEDAGOGY

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Abstract. *Methodological unity of socio-economic development, spiritual heritage - introduction to the main educational ideas of folk pedagogy, the main goal and tasks of the science of folk pedagogy.*

Keywords: *folk pedagogy, education, spiritual and educational heritage, national values, artistic and aesthetic values, heritage of great Eastern thinkers, educational methods.*

Introduction.

At each stage of human history, the direction of development is determined on the basis of the methodological unity of socio-economic development. This law was a factor in the development of science, art, culture, production and lifestyle, which are forms of social consciousness based on socio-economic views, ideas and ideals prevailing in the society. In this way, during the historical development, the rich spiritual heritages collected in connection with the education and upbringing of a well-rounded person have found their expression in the folk pedagogy. Therefore, in the preparation of the future pedagogic staff, it is this spiritual heritage - by introducing them to the main ideas of folk pedagogy related to education, that they acquire knowledge, skills and qualifications that prepare the ground for effective use in pedagogical activity. it is necessary that we focus on health.

Research materials and methodology.

The peoples of Central Asia, in particular, the Uzbek people and their cultural and educational development have developed over the centuries, the ideas of education have embodied the essence of social and political processes of different periods. These enlightened thoughts and ideas created by our people, the rich heritage of education and training have brought up thousands of generations with universal human qualities. Therefore, it is not for nothing that folk pedagogy, which is the heritage of our ancestors, is called a rare field of folk wisdom and etiquette.

For centuries, folk pedagogy has played an important role in the moral, educational formation and maturity of our ancestors. For example, the nation reflected its spiritual-educational, artistic-aesthetic views, philosophical-ethical concepts, life, educational-educational conclusions in folk pedagogy. An important direction of folk pedagogy is the implementation of national education, and one of its important features is to ensure the preservation of national characteristics. It should be noted that the pedagogical views of folk pedagogy, the ideas expressed by our scholars about the organization of the educational process and the teacher's human qualities and professional training have not lost their value even today. Raising a mature person has been one of the urgent problems at all stages of human society. The analysis of the pedagogical views of our people shows that there is a very rich spiritual and educational heritage in this regard. Therefore, introducing the future pedagogical staff to the rich spiritual and educational heritage and pedagogical views of our people on the theory and practice of education prepares the ground for professional and pedagogical training.

The main research object of folk pedagogy is the process of familiarization with the rich spiritual and educational heritage and pedagogical ideas of our people, which have been collected according to the moral, educational and educational views of our people. In this process, the following are studied:

- spiritual-educational and national values of our people; child education in the family, education methods, methods and tools; moral standards of the Uzbek people, culture of behavior;
- reflection of nature and human relations, healthy lifestyle in folk pedagogy; pedagogical ideas of the great thinker;
- the educational value of folklore and epics; the importance of national customs, rituals, traditions, customs, folk games and toys as a means of education; religious teachings in folk pedagogy;
- folk arts, crafts, etc. in folk pedagogy.

Search results

The main goal of the science of folk pedagogy - is the formation and expansion of pedagogical thinking in the future pedagogical personnel, the rich spiritual and educational heritage and pedagogical views of our people collected on the organization of the teaching process and the theory of education. It is to gain the professional and pedagogical training of students by introducing them to their educational opportunities.

Tasks of science - rich educational experience of folk pedagogy, methods of education, human qualities and values, Eastern and Turkic traditions of folk pedagogy, It consists in studying the issues of expression of educational processes in folklore, national traditions, religious teachings and explaining its content to the future generation. The most advanced and unique ideas and opinions of folk pedagogy, which is one of the spiritual culture of our people, the methods, tools, skills and qualifications used in education have lost their value and importance even in our time. not frozen.

National values and its role in educating a well-rounded person. Folk pedagogy is a universal, popular pedagogy in the literal sense. It cannot be imagined outside the history of peoples, people's philosophy, psychology, ethnography, and folk medicine. Also, folk pedagogy is the best example in the fields of science such as pedagogy, philology, ethics, psychology, classic literature, art, oral creativity, it covers all aspects of life, thinking, manners and education. The reason for such influence, importance and vitality of folk pedagogy is, firstly, its vitality, effectiveness, vitality, richness, and secondly, its creation in living traditions in the life process of the people, life and human problems. coverage, aimed at solving the most urgent issues of education, thirdly, it is aimed at a universal direction, a universal idea and goals".

The issues of using all the possibilities of folk pedagogy in raising a perfect, morally pure, mature in all respects, dedicated to his people and homeland, physically fit young people determine the purpose of studying this subject. For example, it is important to explain the nature of national and spiritual values to the next generation. It is known that the people themselves are the ones who create values and transmit them from generation to generation. Therefore, in folk pedagogy, values are widely studied pedagogically, in which they are manifested in the following forms: family values, labor values, values representing household life, values of socio-political content, cultural-educational values, artistic-aesthetic values, values related to a healthy lifestyle, spiritual-spiritual values.

Family values include mutual relations valued by family and family members, respect for elders, respect for children, and affection between relatives. Values related to a healthy lifestyle include the methods of upbringing of our people to make their children healthy, brave and patriotic. Including folk art, handicrafts, music, dance, singing, visual arts, national holidays, customs, traditions, wedding spectacles, mourning ceremonies, dress culture and administration into artistic and aesthetic values. possible. Spiritual and spiritual values consist of qualities such as hard work, humanity, kindness, and generosity, while social and political values include concepts such as justice, peace-loving, freedom, friendship, and equality. Labor values include crafts, farming, animal husbandry, and human household values include national dishes, folk medicine, and Eastern hospitality.

Discussions.

Cultural and educational values include various monuments, mausoleums, historical ensembles, mosques, madrasahs. Scientific and spiritual values include scientific sources, logic, philosophy, mathematics, geometry, algebra, geography, astrology, literature, science, which are important for human development. -Islam (Islamic science) is included. So, as we mentioned above, folk pedagogy reflects our nation's heroic past, national values, history, traditions, advanced ideas and experiences in education. In order to study this priceless heritage and use it in the process of education, we must first know from what sources the pedagogical information, knowledge, skills and qualifications collected by the masses of the people are obtained. Already, the sources of folk pedagogy have a number of originality and non-repetition. The following definition of G.N. Volkov, one of the founders of the science of ethnopedagogy, helps to awaken a bright idea about the sources of folk pedagogy: "Folk pedagogy is a complex of pedagogical information and educational experience preserved in folklore, traditions, rituals, children's games and toys, etc".

The incomparableness, effectiveness, versatility of folk pedagogy.

Folk pedagogy embodies all aspects of Uzbek morals, manners and education. Various educational methods and tools are used in it, these methods and tools are extremely diverse and in many ways superior to scientific pedagogy. Because these methods had an impact on the formation of scientific pedagogy. The various educational methods used in folk pedagogy can be summarized as follows.

1. Explaining (learning, getting used to, practicing).
2. Example (giving advice, apologizing, talking about good things, being an example).
3. Advising, teaching (encouragement, persuasion, begging, begging, wishing, approving, thanking, praying, wishing for a white road, etc.).
4. Slander and punishment (banning, scolding, grudge, reprimanding, forcing, blaming, shaming, threatening, hating, swearing, hitting, beating, etc.).

If you look closely, the above four different methods represent a common whole. First, the general picture is explained to the child. When children do not understand things and events, the educator uses the model method, attention is paid to the independent observation of young people. Even those who do not understand will reach the essence of things and events through the advice and training of adults. However, if the children did not understand or did not want to understand, then it was necessary to use the methods of condemnation and punishment. But the people understood well that this is the last resort. Modern scientific pedagogy has proven that condemnation and punishment are the last resort, or rather the least effective.

The main sources of Uzbek folk pedagogy.

Rare examples of folk pedagogy, educational methods and educational effects were implemented through certain means. Waiting for a guest, going to a guest, various work processes, khashars, various gurungs (tea house, wedding ceremonies), celebrations, various celebrations (birthday celebration, bachelor party, bachelor party), competitions, various ceremonies, etc. served as an educational tool. The seed of goodness planted in the heart of a person today will sprout decades later, it is necessary to predict this scientifically. As we all know, our holy books and values, the legacy of great Eastern thinkers always call us to live with honest work, courage, generosity and humility, justice and kindness. Of course, the spirituality, history, unique customs and traditions of any nation or nation cannot be imagined without national values.

Conclusion

In order to facilitate the study and analysis of educational methods, the acquisition of skills and abilities to use these methods in the pedagogical process, we conditionally divide them into several groups: methods of forming social consciousness, methods of forming social behavior and experiences in the process of activity, methods of self-education and methods of stimulation, methods of punishment.

Theory of education – Examples of the rich experience of Eastern thinkers and folk pedagogy on education: The famous scientist Abu-Raykhan Beruni (973-1048) advises the teacher not to bore the student, the subject should be interesting and demonstrative. In his work "India", Beruni calls to respect scientists and scientists. If people, especially kings and judges, respect and appreciate them, the number of scientists will increase, which means that the society will develop, become civilized and flourish. The great scholar Ibn Sina (980-1037) emphasizes that it is the teacher's responsibility and duty to impart knowledge to the student. The teacher thinks about how it should be and shows them the following instructions: Be calm and restrained in relationships with children; Paying attention to the extent to which students are absorbing the knowledge provided; Use of different methods and types of teaching in education; Use of different methods and types of teaching in education; Knowing the memory, perception, ability to acquire knowledge, individual characteristics of students; Ability to separate (separate) the most important of the given knowledge; Education should be understandable to the student, suitable for his age, mental level (level of understanding); It is necessary to make sure that every word is enough to arouse children's emotions.

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